

A Study of the Complex Compounds of *N*-Benzene-sulphonylglycine with some Metal Ions. Part II

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Three new chelating agents *N*-*o*- and *p*-nitro-benzenesulphonylglycines have been prepared to study the effect of nitro-group substitution and its position in the benzene ring on chelating properties of *N*-benzenesulphonylglycine. The compounds isolated are of the types: (1) $M^{n+} (R_oH)_2 (OH) (H_2O)$ where $M^{n+} = Cu^{2+}, Cd^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} ; (2) $M^{n+} (R_mH)_2$ where $M^{n+} = Cu^{2+}$ or Cd^{2+} ; (3) $K_2Hg (R_o)_2$ and $K_2Cu (R_p)_2$ where $R_oH_2 = N$ -*o*-nitrobenzenesulphonylglycine and $R_pH_2 = N$ -*p*-nitrobenzenesulphonylglycine.

In our previous communication¹ the preparation, properties and the stabilities of the metal chelates of *N*-benzenesulphonylglycine (NBSG) were described. In the present paper the preparation and properties of the *ortho*-, *meta*-, and *para*-nitroderivatives of NBSG as well as some metal chelates of *ortho*- and *para* derivatives are described in order to study the effect of substitution in the benzene ring of *N*-benzenesulphonylglycine.

EXPERIMENTAL

The *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzenesulphonylglycines (henceforth to be represented as R_oH_2 , R_mH_2 and R_pH_2 respectively) were prepared by condensing sulphonyl chlorides, obtained by a modified Sandmeyer reaction² starting from the corresponding nitroaniline, with glycine in presence of aqueous alkali. After completion of the reaction, the filtered solution was acidified with HCl (dil.) (upto about pH 2), stirred vigorously when the compound separated. This was filtered and washed with cold water and the product dissolved in minimum amount of saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution. This was filtered and the filtrate extracted with ether and the aqueous phase acidified with HCl (dil.) to precipitate the compound. This was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The product was dried in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method which was preceded by the reduction of the NO_2 -groups as described by Ma *et al.*³ The results of analyses are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	M.P.	Equivalent weight		%Nitrogen		Colour
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
R_oH_2	160°	260.8	260.0	10.55	10.77	Light yellow
R_mH_2	139°	261.1	260.0	10.53	10.77	Almost colourless
R_pH_2	168°	260.3	260.0	10.90	10.77	Pale yellow

1. Ghosh and Majumder, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 943.
2. Meerwin *et al.* *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 841.
3. Ma *et al.* *Microchim. Acta.*, 1957, 368.

Among the freshly crystallised and air-dried products, R_pH_n was peculiar in that it contained one molecule of H_2O (Found equiv, 278.4. Calc. for $R_pH_n \cdot H_2O$; equiv, 278). The reagent on heating to constant weight for 2 hr. at $105^\circ-110^\circ$ lost one molecule of H_2O (Found loss on dehydration: 6.50; Calc. 6.47%). The dried product had an equivalent weight of 260.3 (Calc. 260.0).

These compounds are crystalline, soluble in acetone, ethanol, hot water, etc. and sparingly soluble in cold water, ether, benzene, toluene etc. These are readily soluble in alkalis.

Preparation of the Metal Chelates

(1) $Cu(R_nH)(OH)(H_2O)$. H_2O was prepared like the corresponding mono-compound of $Cu(II)$ with R_nH . Due to presence of nitro-groups the compounds exploded when heated. For analysis, the compound was treated with glacial acetic acid and KI solution, the liberated I_2 being titrated with thiosulphate solution. (Found: Cu, 17.17; N, 7.10. Calc. Cu, 16.95; N, 7.45%).

On heating the blue compound at $105^\circ-110^\circ$ for 2 hr. it turned green and lost one molecule of H_2O only. Loss found, 4.65; Calc. 4.70%. (Found: Cu-17.62; Calc. for $Cu(R_nH)(OH)(H_2O)$ Cu, 17.78%).

(2) $Cu(R_nH)_2$ was prepared like the corresponding bis-chelate $Cu(RH)_2$. (Found: Cu, 10.65; N, 9.34; Calc. Cu, 10.93; N, 9.63%). $Cu(R_nH)_2$ appeared to be more stable with respect to hydrolysis than $Cu(RH)_2$.

(3) $Cd(R_nH)(OH)(H_2O)$ was prepared like compound (1). (Found: Cd, 27.86. Calc. Cd, 27.67%).

(4) $Cd(R_nH)_2$.—Freshly precipitated CdO and R_nH_n in the approximate molar ratio of 1:2.5 were refluxed in aqueous ethanol for several hours. The solution was filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling deposited crystals which were collected and thoroughly washed with pure acetone. (Found: Cd, 17.46; N, 8.52. Calc. Cd, 17.86; N, 8.89%).

(5) $K_nHg(R_n)_2$.—Freshly precipitated HgO was shaken with KR_nH in the molar ratio of 1:1 and warmed. This was filtered from excess HgO and the clear colorless filtrate was evaporated almost to dryness on water bath when a colorless, sticky mass was obtained. To this excess of anhydrous ethanol was added and the substance was scratched with a glass rod when the mass swelled and was converted to a hard lump. This was broken cautiously and the powder was washed with ethanol. (Found: Hg, 25.01; K, 9.72; Calc. Hg, 25.24; K, 9.84%).

(6) $Hg(R_nH)(OH)(H_2O)$: *Method A*.—Powdered $K_nHg(R_n)_2$ was suspended in water and treated with 1N- HNO_3 till the pH of the solution was about 2.5. A white precipitate obtained was collected and washed thoroughly with water and then with acetone. It was dried in air. (Found: Hg, 39.77; N, 5.45; Calc. Hg, 40.56; N, 5.67%).

The compound was acidic and was titrated with KOH solution with phenolphthalein as indicator. (Found: Equiv., 494; Calc. 494.6). This compound behaved as a monobasic acid.

Method B.— $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution in HNO_3 (dil.) was mixed with twice its moles of R_pH_2 , dissolved in ethanol and on raising the pH to about 2.5, a white precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed thoroughly successively with water, ethanol and acetone and dried in air. (Found: Hg, 39.41; N, 5.40. Calc. Hg, 40.56; N, 6.67%).

(7) $\text{K}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}_p)_4$.— $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in HNO_3 (dil.) was mixed with more than two moles of R_pH_2 in 50% aqueous-ethanol and the pH of the medium was raised to about 6 with KOH solution when a bluish green precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and air-dried (Found: Cu, 9.48; N, 8.08. Calc. Cu, 9.63; N, 8.48%). The compound has a very low solubility in (1:1) aqueous ethanol.

DISCUSSION

Sulphonamide derivatives of the amino-acids and other amines are of potential analytical importance⁴. The three isomeric nitro-derivatives of *N*-benzenesulphonylglycine are new and can be obtained in good yield in a high state of purity without much difficulty. These may serve as excellent primary standards in alkalimetry.

Glycine form chelates with many metals. When an amino compound is converted into its sulphonamide derivatives (as in NBSG), the basicity of the amino group is reduced, so that a new salt-forming centre is developed and they exhibit a greatly enhanced selectivity towards their reactions with certain metal ions; in fact they tend to become selective^{4,5} towards IB and IIB metals of the periodic system. This is also borne out by the fact that though ethylenediamine forms chelates with numerous metals, the chelate forming abilities of *N,N'*-dibenzene-sulphonylethylenediamine become practically limited to those metals⁴.

When the N atom in NBSG coordinates with the metal, the electron density on the N atom is reduced as a result of which the H atom loses its electron to the N atom and thus the acidity of the imido group is profoundly enhanced.

In NBSG and its derivatives, the bonding in the chelates is presumably through the N and O atoms. However, the possibility of bonding through the O atom of SO_2 group cannot be ruled out because the sulphonamides may have tautomeric structures, e.g.,

But this is unlikely on the following grounds: (1) The tautomeric equilibrium is largely to the left, particularly in absence of alkali. (2) Structure (I) forms a 5-membered chelate ring and structure (II), a 7-membered ring which is less likely. (3) That chelation may not

4. Majumder, M. N., D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1965.

5. Fiegl, "Chemistry of Specific, Sensitive and Selective Reactions", Academic Press, New York, 1949.

6. Finar, "Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green and Co., 1954, p. 263;

Turner and Harris, "Organic Chemistry", Longmans, 1952, 142-44.

take place through the O atom in structure(II) also follows from the following unpublished

observations: $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{SO}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}_2$ and $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{SO}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\overset{\text{NH}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}\cdot\text{NH}_2$, which in their tautomeric form are capable of forming 5- and 6-membered chelate rings respectively, were found to provide no chelates.

The structure of the bis-chelates may be written as:

Na_2CuR_2 contains one unpaired electron: μ_B found by actual measurement was 1.80 B.M. Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , and Hg^{II} chelates are presumably tetrahedral. The HgR_4^{2-} ion is quite stable⁷ and if it is tetrahedral, it should be optically active. Attempts were made to make fractional crystallisation of the l-quinine salt of H_2HgR_2 , but unfortunately the attempts failed.

$\text{K}_2\text{Hg}(\text{R}_2)_2$ could easily be prepared, but attempts to prepare $\text{H}_2\text{Hg}(\text{R}_2)_2$ always yielded $\text{Hg}(\text{R}_2\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$. Because of increasing steric effects by bulkier substituents on the N atom, the ligands acquire a greater tendency to form hydroxylated species⁸, having lower solubilities than the corresponding bis-chelates. Low solubility of the corresponding mono-compound may be one of the reasons which forces the following hydrolytic equilibrium to the right:

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7. Ghosh and Majumder, *J. Ind. Chem. Sec.*, 1964, 41, 286.

8. Chatt, Duncanson and Venanzi, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem. Symposium*, 1959, 67.